

A ruthenium(II) complex of glyoxalbis(2-methoxyanil) (gmha) and the redox series : Radical non-radical states[†]

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Abstract : The article reports on a glyoxalbis(2-methoxyanil) (gmha) complex of ruthenium(II) of type *cis*-[Ru^{II}(gmha)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (1). Single crystal X-ray bond parameters of the diimine fragment of 1 are severely deformed due to mixing of d_{Ru} and π* orbitals : 1, C=N, 1.308(3), C-C, 1.404(4) Å. The redox activity of 1 is solvent dependent. In CH₂Cl₂, the anodic wave due to Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} couple is reversible, while the cathodic wave due to gmha/gmha^{•-} couple is irreversible. In a mixture of CH₂Cl₂ and CH₃CN (4 : 1) solvents both anodic and cathodic waves at 0.41 and -1.22 V are reversible, while in DMF it exhibits a 2e transfer cathodic wave at -1.17 V due to gmha/gmha²⁻ reduction couple. Spectroelectrochemical measurements, EPR spectra and the density functional theory (DFT) calculations authenticated the electronic structures of 1, 1⁻ and 1⁺. 1⁻ is a hybrid state of *cis*-[Ru^{II}(gmha^{•-})(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁻ (g = 2.002) and *cis*-[Ru^I(gmha²⁻)(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁻ (g₁ = 2.148, g₂ = 2.041 and g₃ = 1.955, A_{Cl} = 15, 33 G) states exhibiting a temperature dependent tautomeric equilibrium of type Ru^{II}(gmha^{•-}) ↔ Ru^I(gmha²⁻), while 1⁺ is a ruthenium(III) complex of type *cis*-[Ru^{III}(gmha)(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁺. The study authenticated that gmha is redox non-innocent.

Keywords : Glyoxalbis(2-methoxyanil), redox non-innocence, diimine anion radical, ruthenium complex.

Introduction

It is documented that the coordinated redox non-innocent fragments expand the reactivity of the metal ions promoting many reactions at the metal centre, which are not expected with redox innocent fragments¹. The redox non-innocent ligands combined to redox active transition metal ions open up an opportunity to participate in multi electron transfer reactions and are potential platforms in exhibiting valence tautomerism (VT)². Thus the coordination chemistry of redox non-innocent fragments is a subject of investigation. In this context, the redox non-innocent α-diimine (L^RR₂') chelate that is an electron acceptor and exists as neutral diimine (L^RR₂'), diimine anion radical (L^RR₂'^{•-}) and di-anionic diimide (L^RR₂'²⁻) as illustrated in Scheme 1, is persuaded³. The bond parameters and the spectral features of these three electronic states, L^RR₂', L^RR₂'^{•-} and L^RR₂'²⁻ in complexes are notably different.

Glyoxalbis(2-hydroxyanil) (gha) is redox non-innocent as depicted in Scheme 2. Recently, the coordination complexes of cobalt(III)⁴ and ruthenium(II/III)⁵ of the gha were

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disclosed⁶. Formation of the trianionic gha^{3-} anion radical was also authenticated in lead(IV), tin(IV)⁷ and uranium(VI)⁸ complexes. In this project, the coordination chemistry of glyoxalbis(2-methoxyanil) (gmha) as shown in Chart 1, which is a neutral analogue of gha was explored, particularly with redox non-innocent ruthenium ion. The coordination complex isolated is *cis*- $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (**1**). In this article, synthesis, spectra, electrochemical studies including the single crystal X-ray structure of **1** are reported. The redox activity of gmha in **1** is solvent dependent. In conjunction with the experimental parameters, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were employed to elucidate the electronic structures of **1**, 1^- and 1^+ ions. It is noted that a significant amount of spin density is shared by the ruthenium ion in 1^- and it is defined by a hybrid state of diimine anion radical coordinated to ruthenium(II) ion and the dianionic diimide coordinated to ruthenium(III) ion.

Experimental

Physical measurements : Spectroscopic grade solvents were used for spectroscopic and electrochemical measurements. The C, H and N contents of the compounds were obtained from a Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series II elemental analyzer. All analyses were performed after drying the samples under high vacuum. Infrared spectra of the samples were measured from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} with KBr pellets at room temperature on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum RX 1 FT-IR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra in CDCl_3 solvent was obtained on a Bruker DPX 500 MHz spectrometer. ESI mass spectra were recorded on a micro mass Q-TOF mass spectrometer and Shimadzu LCMS-2020. Electronic absorption spectra in solution at 298 K were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 750 spectrophotometer in the range 3300–200 nm. Magnetic susceptibilities at 298 K were measured on a Sherwood Magnetic Susceptibility Balance. The X-band electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectra in a temperature range of 298 to 115 K were measured on a Magnostech GmbH MiniScope MS400 spectrometer (equipped with temperature controller TC H03), where the microwave frequency was measured with an FC400 frequency counter. The EPR spectra were simulated using Easy Spin software package. The electro analytical instrument BASi Epsilon-EC was used for cyclic

voltammetric experiments and spectroelectrochemistry measurements.

Materials : Reagents or analytical-grade materials were obtained from commercial suppliers and used without further purification. The precursor $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2]$ was prepared by a reported procedure⁹.

Glyoxalbis(2-methoxyanil) (gmha) : To a 40% aqueous solution of glyoxal (3 mmol), 2-methoxyaniline (800 mg, 6.5 mmol) was added and mixed well with a glass rod. The mixture turned reddish brown. To the brown mass, methanol (15 mL) was added and stirred for 2 h at 310 K. A suspension was obtained, which was filtered and the residue was dried in air. Yield : 0.59 g (~73% with respect to glyoxal). ESI (positive ion)-MS in CH_3OH ; m/z : 267.31 (gmha); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 500 MHz, 295 K) δ (ppm) : 7.25 (2H, s), 7.04 (2H, d), 6.97 (2H, t), 6.72 (2H, t), 6.59 (2H, d), 3.98 (6H, s). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ (gmha) : C, 71.62; H, 6.01; N, 10.44. Found : C, 71.54; H, 5.97; N, 10.36; IR (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 3047 (w, $\nu_{\text{C-H(aryl)}}$), 2916 (m, $\nu_{\text{C-H(aliph)}}$), 1587 (vs, $\nu_{\text{CPh=N-}}$), 1517 (vs), 1482 (s), 1343 (s), 1296 (s), 1175 (w), 820 (s), 628 (w), 506 (w).

***cis*- $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (**1**)** : To a solution of gmha (30 mg, 0.1 mmol) in EtOH (30 mL), $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2]$ (100 mg, 0.1 mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 45 min and allowed to cool to room temperature (298 K). Dark purple microcrystals of **1** separated out, which were filtered, collected and dried in air. Yield : 46 mg (~66% with respect to ruthenium). Single crystals for X-ray structure determination were obtained by diffusion of *n*-hexane to the dark purple dichloromethane solution of **1**. ESI (positive ion)-MS in CH_3OH ; m/z : 667.04 $[\text{1-Cl}]^+$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 500 MHz, 295 K) δ (ppm) : 7.85 (2H, s), 7.47 (1H, t), 7.31–7.06 (19H, m), 6.92 (2H, t), 6.47 (1H, d), 4.09 (3H, s), 3.17 (3H, s). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{PRuCl}_2$ (**1**) : C, 58.12; H, 4.45; N, 3.99. Found : C, 58.05; H, 4.37; N, 3.91; IR (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 3052 (w, $\nu_{\text{C-H(aryl)}}$), 2935 (w, $\nu_{\text{C-H(aliph)}}$), 1592 (s, $\nu_{\text{CPh=N-}}$), 1489 (s), 1436 (vs), 1448 (vs), 1273 (w), 1114 (s), 1092 (s), 1020(s), 751(m), 697 (vs, $\nu_{\text{Ru-P(sym)}}$), 525 (vs, $\nu_{\text{Ru-P(asym)}}$), 512 (vs).

cis-[Ru^{II}(gmha^{•-})(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁻ (**1⁻**) and *cis*-[Ru^{III}(gmha)(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁺ (**1⁺**): These complexes were not isolated chemically. However, these were generated electrochemically for spectrochemical measurements and EPR spectra.

X-Ray crystallographic data collection and refinement of the structure (CCDC 1434541): Single crystals of **1** (red) was picked up with nylon loops and mounted on a Bruker Kappa-CCD and (at 296 K) diffractometer equipped with a Mo-target rotating anode X-ray source and a graphite monochromator (Mo K α , $\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). Final cell constants were obtained from least-squares fits of all measured reflections. Structures were readily solved by Patterson methods and subsequent difference Fourier techniques. The crystallographic data are given in Table 1. ShelXS97^{10a} and ShelXL97^{10b-c} were used for the structure solution and refinement. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms were placed at calculated positions and refined as riding atoms with isotropic displacement parameters.

Table 1. Crystallographic data of **1** (CCDC 1434541)

Formula	C ₃₄ H ₃₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ PRu
Fw	702.55
Crystal colour	Dark red
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i>
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.6970(16)
<i>b</i> (Å)	22.996(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	12.963(2)
β°/γ°	107.563(3)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	3040.0(8)
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>T</i> (K)	293(2)
Calcd. (g cm ⁻³)	1.535
Unique reflections	5367
Reflection (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	4228
λ , Å (μ , mm ⁻¹)	0.71073/0.779
<i>F</i> (000)	1432
R1 ^a [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]/GoF ^b	0.0336/1.036
R1 ^a (all data)	0.0482
wR2 ^c (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	0.0724
No. of parameters	381
Residual density (eÅ ⁻³)	0.409
^a R1 = $\Sigma F_o - F_c /\Sigma F_o $. ^b GOF = $\{\Sigma[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2]/(n-p)\}^{1/2}$. ^c wR2 = $[\Sigma[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2]/\Sigma[w(F_o^2)^2]]^{1/2}$ where $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (aP)^2 + bP]$, $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.	

Density functional theory (DFT) and time dependent (TD) DFT calculations: All calculations reported in this article were done with the Gaussian 03W¹¹ program package supported by GaussView 4.1. The DFT¹² and TD DFT¹³ calculations were performed at the level of a Becke three-parameter hybrid functional with the nonlocal correlation functional of Lee-Yang-Parr (B3LYP)¹⁴. Gas-phase geometries of the ligand and the complex were optimized using Pulay's direct inversion¹⁵ in the iterative subspace (DIIS), "tight" convergent SCF procedure¹⁶, ignoring symmetry. The geometries of gmha and *cis*-[Ru(gmha)(PMe₃)Cl₂] (**1^{Me}**) were optimized with singlet spin state, while *cis*-[Ru(gmha)(PMe₃)Cl₂]⁻ (**1^{Me-}**) and *cis*-[Ru(gmha)(PMe₃)Cl₂]⁺ (**1^{Me+}**) were optimized with doublet spin state. In all calculations, a LANL2DZ basis set along with the corresponding effective core potential (ECP) was used for nickel, ruthenium and rhodium metals¹⁷. The valence double- ζ basis set 6-31G¹⁸ for H was used. For the non-hydrogen atoms C, N, O, P, and Cl, valence double- ζ with diffuse and polarization functions, 6-31+G*¹⁹ as basis set was employed for all calculations. The 60 lowest singlet excitation energies on each of the optimized geometries of **1** was calculated by the TD DFT method²⁰.

Results and discussion

Details of the preparation of gmha and the complex are outlined in the Experimental section. **1** was prepared by a reaction of gmha with [Ru^{II}(PPh₃)₃Cl₂] precursor in boiling ethanol. **1** and gmha were characterized by elemental analyses, mass, IR and ¹H NMR spectra. Data are summarized in the Experimental section. In comparison to the free gmha ligand, the stretching frequency ($\nu_{C=N}$) of the aldimine functions are red shifted in the complex. It is authenticated that gha is a tetradentate N₂O₂-donor ligand, while gmha acts as a tridentate NNO-donor ligand as depicted in Chart 1.

Molecular geometries: Single crystal X-ray structure determination confirmed the molecular geometry of **1**. The diffraction study confirmed the NNO coordination of the gmha ligand to the ruthenium(II) ion keeping two Cl ligands *cis* to each other. **1** crystallizes in the *P*2₁/*n* space group. The molecular geometry in the crystals and the atom labeling scheme are shown in Fig. 1. The relevant bond parameters are listed in Table 2. The diimine frag-

Fig. 1. Molecular geometry of **1** in crystals (40% thermal ellipsoids).

Table 2. Selected experimental bond lengths (Å) of **1** and the corresponding calculated parameters of *cis*-[Ru^{II}(gmha)(PMe₃)Cl₂] (**1**^{Me}), **1**^{Me-} and **1**^{Me+}

	Expt.	Calcd.		
		1 ^{Me}	1 ^{Me-}	1 ^{Me+}
Ru(1)-N(2)	1.949(2)	1.972	2.006	2.010
Ru(1)-N(3)	1.997(2)	2.039	2.080	2.305
Ru(1)-Cl(1)	2.433(1)	2.497	2.572	2.395
Ru(1)-Cl(2)	2.427(1)	2.464	2.531	2.378
Ru(1)-P(2)	2.314(2)	2.359	2.302	2.463
Ru(1)-O(2)	2.229(2)	2.273	2.294	2.265
C(31)-C(32)	1.404(4)	1.418	1.391	1.424
N(3)-C(31)	1.306(4)	1.324	1.353	1.324
N(2)-C(32)	1.310(4)	1.325	1.356	1.316
N(3)-C(23)	1.425(4)	1.423	1.404	1.418
N(2)-C(1)	1.411(4)	1.409	1.374	1.404
C(6)-O(2)	1.386(4)	1.379	1.391	1.387

ment incorporating the ruthenium and chlorine atoms and the coordinated anisole fragment excluding the methyl group is planar with a mean deviation of 0.03 Å. The dihedral angle between this plane and the pendent anisole ring is 66.5°. In **1**, two anisole methyl groups orient *trans* to each other. The Ru^{II}-O length is 2.229(2) Å. The average Ru^{II}-N_{imine} lengths are 1.973(2) Å. The average Ru^{II}-Cl lengths are 2.429(2) Å. The diimine fragment of **1** is deformed. The average C=N lengths, 1.308(2) Å, are longer than expected, 1.24 ± 1 Å^{3e}, while the C-C length is relatively shorter, 1.404(4) Å.

EPR spectra : Coulometric reduction of **1** in CH₂Cl₂ containing 20% CH₃CN afforded **1**⁻ ion. The EPR spectra of CH₂Cl₂ solution at 298 K and CH₂Cl₂ frozen glass of **1**⁻ ion at 115 K were recorded and are depicted in Fig. 2. The fluid solution isotropic EPR spectrum of **1**⁻

ion as illustrated Fig. 2(a) corresponds to *g* = 2.002, which is consistent to the existence of the Ru^{II}(gmha^{•-}) state. However, the frozen glass EPR spectrum is anisotropic due to the contribution of Ru^I(gmha²⁻) state in **1**⁻. The spectrum of **1**⁻ ion was simulated considering *cis*-[Ru^I(gmha²⁻)(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁻ and *cis*-[Ru^{II}(gmha^{•-})(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁻ constituents as depicted in Fig. 2b. The simulated *g* parameters are : **1**⁻, *g*₁ = 2.148, *g*₂ = 2.041 and *g*₃ = 1.955, *g*_{max} - *g*_{min} (Δg) = 0.19 due to the former component and *g* = 2.001 for the later organic radical component. The spectrum of the *cis*-[Ru^I(gmha²⁻)(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁻ component was simulated considering the hyperfine coupling due to ^{35,37}Cl (*I* = 3/2) nuclei as depicted in Fig. 2b(iii)²¹. The relatively lower anisotropy predicts a lower contribution of the ruthenium(III) state in **1**⁻ ion.

The anisotropic EPR spectrum of the CH₂Cl₂ frozen glass of **1**⁺ ion as illustrated in Fig. 2(c), infer the formation of the ruthenium(III) complex of type *cis*-[Ru^{III}(gmha)(PPh₃)Cl₂]⁺ upon oxidation of **1**. The simulated *g* parameters as listed in Table 3, are similar to those reported in cases of ruthenium(III) complexes incorporating redox non-innocent diimine fragments^{22,23}.

Electrochemical studies : The redox activities of gmha and **1** were investigated by cyclic voltammetry in CH₂Cl₂ at 298 K as shown in Fig. 3. The redox potential data referenced to the ferrocenium/ferrocene (Fc⁺/Fc) couple are summarized in Table 4. It is observed that the cathodic and anodic waves of the gmha ligand at 298 K due to gmha/gmha^{•-} and gmha^{•+}/gmha redox couples are irreversible. The gmha/gmha^{•-} couple is more reversible in **1**. In CH₂Cl₂, the anodic wave due to ruthenium(III)/ruthenium(II) couple is reversible, while the cathodic wave due to gmha/gmha^{•-} couple is irreversible as shown in Fig. 3a(i). However, in a mixture of CH₂Cl₂ and CH₃CN (4 : 1) solvents both anodic and cathodic waves at 0.41 and -1.22 V are reversible as illustrated in Fig. 3(b). In DMF, it is noted that the current height of the cathodic wave is double to that of the anodic wave (Fig. 3a(ii)). This cathodic wave at -1.17 V is assigned to gmha/gmha²⁻ reduction couple which is a 2e transfer process. It authenticates that the gmha ligand is redox non-innocent.

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations and electronic structures : In conjunction with the X-ray bond parameters and EPR spectra, DFT calculations at the

Fig. 2. X-band EPR spectra of (a) 1^- (CH_2Cl_2 solution at 298 K), (b) 1^- (CH_2Cl_2 frozen glass at 115 K) : (i) black, experimental spectrum; (ii) red, simulated spectrum considering the two components, $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{2-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ and $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ (1 : 1); (iii) green, simulated spectrum considering the pure component of $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{2-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$; (iv) blue, simulated spectrum considering the pure component of $\text{trans-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ and (c) 1^+ (CH_2Cl_2 frozen glass at 115 K) : (i) experimental, (ii) simulated).

Table 3. X-band EPR spectral parameters 1^- and 1^+ ions

Complexes	g_1	g_2	g_3	g_{av}	Δg	Coupling constant (A/G)
1^- (CH_2Cl_2 at 298 K)		2.002		2.002		
1^- (frozen glass at 115 K)						
components :						
$\text{Ru}^{\text{I}}(\text{gmha}^{2-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$	2.139	2.038	1.950	2.042	0.19	$^{35,37}\text{Cl}$ ($I = 3/2$), $A_1 = 15$, $A_2 = 33$
$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$		2.001		2.001		
1^+ (frozen glass at 115 K)	2.210	2.090	2.072	2.124	0.14	$^{99,101}\text{Ru}$ ($I = 5/2$), $A_1 = 112$, $A_2 = 3.3$, $A_3 = 30$

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 in (a) (CH_2Cl_2 (i), DMF (ii) and (b) CH_2Cl_2 and CH_3CN (4 : 1) solvents mixture at 298 K.

Table 4. Redox potential data of gmha and 1 at 298 K

	$E_{1/2}$ (V) (ΔE^c , mV)	$E_{1/2}$ (V) (ΔE^c , mV)
gmha	+0.676 ^a	-1.81 ^b
1 (CH_2Cl_2)	+0.41 (92)	-1.43 (147) ^b
1 ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{MeCN}$)	+0.41 (115)	-1.22 (170)
1 (DMF)	-0.035 (70)	-1.17 (220)

^aAnodic peak, ^bcathodic peak, ^cpeak-to-peak separation.

Conditions : 0.20 M $[\text{N}(\text{n-Bu})_4]\text{PF}_6$ supporting electrolyte; platinum working electrode; scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹.

B3LYP level of the theory were employed to elucidate the electronic structures of 1 , 1^- and 1^+ . The electronic structures of 1 , 1^- and 1^+ were investigated by optimizing the gas phase geometries of $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PMe}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$ (1^{Me}),

$\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})(\text{PMe}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ ($1^{\text{Me}-}$) and $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PMe}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^+$ ($1^{\text{Me}+}$) with singlet, doublet and doublet spin states. Selected bond parameters are summarized in Table 2. The closed shell singlet (CSS) solution of 1 is stable confirming the coordination of neutral gmha ligand to ruthenium(II) ion as in $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$ (1). In comparison to those of 1^{Me} , the C=N lengths of $1^{\text{Me}-}$ are relatively longer (avg. 1.355 Å) while the C-C length of the diimine fragment is shorter (1.391 Å). The feature is consistent to the reduction of diimine fragment of gmha in $1^{\text{Me}-}$ ion. In $1^{\text{Me}-}$ the atomic densities are primarily localized on the diimine fragment as illustrated in Fig. 4a. However, a significant amount of spin density (~19%) is localized on one of the t_{2g} orbitals of ruthenium ion. Thus 1^- is defined as a hybrid state of $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^- \leftrightarrow \text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha}^{2-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ states. Localization of Mulliken spin density on ruthenium ion of $1^{\text{Me}+}$ as given in Fig. 4b authenticated that 1^+ ion is a ruthenium(III) complex.

Electronic spectra, spectroelectrochemical measurements and time dependant (TD) DFT calculations : The UV-Vis absorption spectra of 1 depend on solvent. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of gmha was recorded in CH_2Cl_2 , while the UV-Vis spectra of 1 were recorded in

Fig. 4. Atomic spin density plots of (a) 1^{Me-} and (b) 1^{Me+} (isovalue = 0.004) obtained from the Mulliken spin population analyses.

CH_2Cl_2 , $CH_2Cl_2 + CH_3CN$ (4 : 1) and DMF at 298 K. The spectra are shown in Fig. 5 and the absorption spectral data are summarized in Table 5. The origin of the lower energy absorption bands of the complex was elucidated by the TD DFT calculations on 1^{Me} in CH_2Cl_2 using CPCM model. The excitation energies with the oscil-

lator strengths and the transition types are also summarized in Table 6. The gmha ligand exhibits UV absorption band at 385 nm due to $\pi_{Ar-SMe} \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition (Fig. 5a). The lower energy absorption band of **1** at 539 nm is assigned to $d_{Ru} \rightarrow \pi^*$ MLCT transition, the calculated wavelength is 519.18 nm.

Fig. 5. UV-Vis spectra of (a) gmha in CH_2Cl_2 , (b) **1** in CH_2Cl_2 , (c) **1** in CH_2Cl_2/CH_3CN (4 : 1) and (d) **1** in DMF at 298 K.

Table 5. UV-Vis absorption spectral data

Compounds	λ_{max}/nm (ϵ , $10^{-4} M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)
gmha (CH_2Cl_2)	385 (0.06), 288 (0.89)
1 (CH_2Cl_2)	540 (0.10), 394 (0.26)
1 (CH_2Cl_2/CH_3CN)	605 (0.22), 488 (1.21), 400 (1.23), 326 (1.17)
1 (DMF)	520 (0.31), 385 (0.59)
1^- (CH_2Cl_2/CH_3CN)	584 (0.27), 481 (0.91), 397 (1.06), 312 (1.27)
1^+ (CH_2Cl_2)	493 (0.31), 386(0.79)

The UV-Vis/NIR absorption spectrum of 1^+ was recorded in CH_2Cl_2 by the spectroelectrochemical measurements at 298 K and absorption data are summarized in Table 5. The changes of electronic spectra during the conversions of $1 \rightarrow 1^-$ in $CH_2Cl_2 + CH_3CN$ (4 : 1) and $1 \rightarrow 1^+$ in CH_2Cl_2 are illustrated respectively in Fig. 6a and 6b.

Table 6. UV-Vis absorption spectral data and calculated excitation energies (λ /nm), oscillation strengths (f) and transition types of $\mathbf{1}^{\text{Me}}$ obtained from TD DFT calculations in CH_2Cl_2				
λ_{exp} (nm)	$\lambda_{\text{calcd.}}$ (nm)	f	Significant contributions (> 12%)	Transition types
539 (0.10)	519.18	0.05	HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO (38%)	$\text{p}_{\text{Cl}} + \text{d}_{\text{Ru}} \rightarrow \pi^*$
444 (0.14)	464	0.18	HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO (46%)	$\text{p}_{\text{Cl}} \rightarrow \pi^*$
391 (0.26)	395.70	0.18	HOMO-5 \rightarrow LUMO (32%)	$\text{p}_{\text{Cl}} + \text{d}_{\text{Ru}} + \pi_{\text{aromatic}} \rightarrow \pi^*$
			HOMO-4 \rightarrow LUMO (14%)	$\text{p}_{\text{Cl}} + \pi_{\text{aromatic}} \rightarrow \pi^*$

Fig. 6. Spectroelectrochemical measurements showing the change of electronic spectra during the conversions of (a) $\mathbf{1} \rightarrow \mathbf{1}^-$ in $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ (4 : 1) and (b) $\mathbf{1} \rightarrow \mathbf{1}^+$ in CH_2Cl_2 at 298 K.

Conclusion

A ruthenium(II) complex of glyoxalbis(2-methoxyanil) (gmha) incorporating triphenyl phosphine and chloride as co-ligands, of type $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$ ($\mathbf{1}$) is reported. Molecular geometries and the bond parameters of $\mathbf{1}$ were determined by single crystal X-ray structure determination. The alpha diimine fragment of gmha in $\mathbf{1}$ is significantly deformed due to the mixing of d_{Ru} and π^* orbitals. In a CH_2Cl_2 and CH_3CN (4 : 1) solvents mixture both $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{gmha}/\text{gmha}^{\bullet-}$ reduction couples are reversible. In DMF it exhibits a 2e transfer reduction wave may be due to $\text{gmha}/\text{gmha}^{2-}$ couple. Electronic structures of $\mathbf{1}^+$ and $\mathbf{1}^-$ were established using the EPR spectra and density functional theory (DFT) calculations. $\mathbf{1}$ is a ruthenium(II) complex of neutral gmha. $\mathbf{1}^+$ ion is a gmha complex of ruthenium(III) of type $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^+$. $\mathbf{1}^-$ exhibits a temperature dependent tautomeric equilibrium of type $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^- \rightarrow \text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{2-})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^-$. Thus $\mathbf{1}^-$ ion is defined as a hybrid state of $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})$ and $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{2-})$ states. The CH_2Cl_2 frozen glass EPR spectrum of $\mathbf{1}^-$ is anisotropic due to higher contribution of $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{gmha}^{2-})$ state, while in fluid solution the contribution of $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha}^{\bullet-})$ state dominates and attributes an isotropic EPR signal at $g = 2.002$. The atomic spin densi-

ties of $\mathbf{1}^-$ ion scatter on both ruthenium ($\sim 19\%$) and alpha diimine backbone authenticated by the Mulliken spin population analysis. In summary, the work authenticated that gmha is redox non-innocent and promotes a new electron transfer series of types, $\text{cis-}[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{gmha})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Cl}_2]^z$ ($z = 1+, 0, 1-, 2-$).

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